

A CREATIVE ENTREPRENEUR AND LEGAL PROCESS THROUGH TECHNO-PRENEURSHIP BY EMPLOYEE ISSUES: EVIDENCE ON MALANG, EAST JAVA

NI WAYAN SRI ARIYANI*

Faculty of Engineering, Universitas Udayana, Indonesia. Corresponding Author Email: sriariyani@unud.ac.id

Abstract

Objectives: This research study aims to analyze the impact between entrepreneur and local business mechanisms with regulation. **Methodology:** This research is a qualitative research and using an online questionnaire to collect the data from local people as a participant. This study uses non-probability sampling with purposive sampling. The data analysis technique was used is meta-analysis. **Results:** The results were showed by the impact in business platform industry. In contrast, an advantages of business are relatively straightforward with a new strategy. Besides that, a high demand for young entrepreneur becoming available in Indonesia, which is entrepreneur be able to sell up their product with legal system. In term of many rules, as an entrepreneur can survive with factoring system for local communities by pride local wisdom version off. This research study had opportunity such as new insight, experience, and influence rather than attempting to memorize business concepts. However, the business preparation with legal system would be find out inner creativity during pandemic covid-19. So, the creative entrepreneur would now becoming manager in business platform area such as responsibility and legal regulation.

Keywords: Young Generation, Economic Outlook, Creative Entrepreneur, Malang

INTRODUCTION

This research should determine what a job description to be successful and should believe in the mission of an organization or a local community and not just want to get a job without soft skills, hard skills, and knowledge about legal system. A creative entrepreneur should have appreciation of creative unique product, during the interview for business process both mission and value added. Research by Hodges (2017) stated that a lot of potentials employees are looking for places to work where they felt that they are make a difference and did not just performs a job.

According to Lozano (2018) stated that a creative entrepreneurs have a contract by legal system for this type of work, which is particularly important as the work might be done remotely. This arrangement does not allow for easy review of the work in business progress, leaving an entrepreneur vulnerable to poor-quality as a complete work. However, communication expectations and review of work in business progress need to be written down to ensure a final product acceptable to learn about legal system. Ultimately, a basis of payment whether hourly or by business project. It should be explained in detail to catch up failure systems in Malang areas.

Many countries are requirement business to register an existence with some government and requirement business to pay fees for just being in being platform areas in the world. Additionally, fee might be charge if the business was located in special business improvement

zone. These business zone absolutely area created by a local economic development authorities to access on each business a fee that pays for services beyond what is provided by the government. However, registration for a business supplies are needed many more information such government and agencies to assess fees in Malang.

Mostly, a creative entrepreneur's in Malang, which would rather spent their time to create a unique product both quality and quantity. After this, spending a lot of time to learn about reading tax regulations. Therefore, it has been engage a few service of a professional to prepare tax forms and make payments might be a good investment.

TEORITICAL FRAMEWORK

Creative Entrepreneurs

As creative entrepreneurs will discover that there are number of legal and management system issues with business and economic grow. For instance, a creative entrepreneurs would need to understand the basics to contracts and copyright any challenging of business. It not mean that they should not also seek out any professional a legal advice. Additionally, all creative entrepreneurs should have a basic understanding for copyright issues, licensing, leasing, zoning, and permits.

There is an old saying that the only one to certainties in social life both economic and business issues in Indonesia. While, this can understanding a basic principles of taxation, which is necessity for everyone, business must particularly consider how taxes would impact to their profits. As their business grows, any creative entrepreneur might also decide about some people need to hire staff to handle and to increase workload in the time like productive, absolutely catch up maximum by economic activities. However, a basic of recruitment and hire employees are part of the management skills needed by a creative entrepreneurs.

A legal aspects about contracts, copyright, zoning, permits, and renting or leasing some property would vary types from country to country in the world. In fact, they might even vary between cities in the same country like Indonesia. Some legal systems would like provide more protection to management. While, others might seek to protect any employees. In the some countries, property contracts are flexible, while in others the terms are non-negotiable. Because of an information about business and legal system is meant to highlight with the most common issues facing people that manage their own business. Ultimately, in all cases given a lot of advice that must be sought to ensure like applicable laws are being followed.

Signing contracts

While, a legal issues would vary based on the country, there are a basic contract situations and terms that pertain to a creative entrepreneurs almost everywhere. For instance, the specific components about a legal contract would vary, but a business purpose of contract, which is reduce a risk, to all parties involved. More money in any business situation, more risks, and therefore to have contract. For instance, if a creative entrepreneurs lend a friend for some money to buy lunch that they might not felt the need for a contract, then to ensure repayment.

Generally, if they are lending some business friends about cost to buy a home, it would be foolish and not have any contract.

Hiring Employee

A decision has been made to hire some paperwork that would be start it day to day. Firstly, an application was unsuccessful applicants, along with notes explain that why they were not chosen, need to be maintain. Generally, this is a legal purposes in case applicants can decide about they were not hired for discriminatory business reason. Secondly, a paperwork was associated by hiring the successful candidate needs to be prepare. Some formal contract might not be needed, but some a new employee should be provided with written a job description. Absolutely, they will work some schedule and pay amount that familiar for business policies.

Ultimately, besides being paid some salaries both employer and employee might need to pay employment taxes that are mandated by the government to cover social security and disability compensation business plan. Additionally, some benefits might be either mandated or offered include vacation paid, sick paid, health coverage, and pension plan in the future. In contrast, a creative entrepreneur must understand the detail of legal issues that would result from hiring staff. Eventually, if benefits were not mandated with creative entrepreneur might wish to offer benefits, so as to attract a good and capable employees.

METHODOLOGY

This research study aims to conduct a legal system with business issues to take each opportunity and to connect a local community that young generations are passionate it in Malang City. For instance, local product, target market, or simply competitive business driven to achieve goals in digital platform industry by a good and capability employees. Various passion for business performance both skills, education, and personal traits are required to do the best job that suitable with a legal issues.

Based on these business research areas, it was used by key words with new ideas, local product, and strategy with legal system. Many articles are search by online databases through www.sciencedirect.com published from 2013 to 2022 and books related to creative, entrepreneurs, legal system, and business local areas in Malang, East Java.

This research had some criteria such as:

1. Scientific articles have been discussed by business capacity for economic, management, and law as independent variables, associated by business issues.
2. Articles using in English text or sources
3. Articles have published years from 2013-2022

Based on predetermined criteria, 10 articles were captured by initial stage which was discussed by unique business ideas and different process for win as a young entrepreneur. This research methodology had sorting through a legal regulation and viewed by valuable time for business startup.

RESULTS

Rather than relying on potential customers to find the website, a creative entrepreneur have the choice for using an established online marketplace. These are tourism platform industries that host websites and can be used with creative entrepreneur for displaying and selling many more local product in Malang, East Java. They will range from digital market place by technology and sell inexpensive handcrafted items to ones. After this, a strategy to sell major work both traditional and modern expenditure between a local community like art to collectors.

A quick online search would provide an up to date for list of choices about business plan to increase economic grow. These sites vary on as to the types of products that are sold and the types for customers targeted. Some are for any type of creative product, while others specialize in an art form to upgrade some rules of business in Malang.

This business sites would like vary by the services that they can provide to the creative entrepreneur with some providing only a basic software and customized by digital platform industries to catch up all customers in the world.

In the other sites, offer traditional design services and a community for fellow artists that could be asked for advice. Generally, a creative entrepreneur might be charge a flat fee, list pee per item, a percentage fee on each sale or any combination to these charges. However, a creative entrepreneur must not simply used with the first online market place that they find a best quality of unique product from Malang. Nevertheless, it can follow the same selection with business process that they would follow when considering a retail store. Ultimately, these online market places vary as to affordable price, a quality of products, customers targeted, and brand image, just as do brick and mortar stores in zero point of Malang.

Such sites are not meant to replace other means and to promote some product. For this reason, some creative young entrepreneur who use online market place absolutely to sell their economic activities should also still maintain their own web and social media sites as. In contrast, it is on these sites that creative entrepreneurs build their reputation.

CONCLUSION

While dealing some legal topics might not be know about creative entrepreneur wish to spend their time, so they are necessary to understand the part of business survive. Contact dealing with some property, commissioning and consignment to work that would be part of doing business. A creative entrepreneur would need to seek the advice of experts on many of these issues, but still needs a basic understand for contract components. Copyright to protect the work of creative entrepreneur must be understood for business issues that deal with licensing, leasing, and zoning to deal about ongoing basis in the life of entrepreneur. However, this is about another unavoidable business issue is taxation. In contrast, if a creative entrepreneur would decided to hire employees, so management tasks such as a job analysis, recruitment, interviews, and hiring must be undertaken in discuss some rule of business in a local district area like Malang areas.

References

- 1) A. Langley, C. Abdallah. (2011). Templates and turns in qualitative studies of strategy and management. *Res. Metho. Strateg. Manage*, volume 6, pages 201-235.
- 2) Caporale, Bob. (2015). *Creative Strategy Generation Using Passion and Creativity to Compose Business Strategy That Inspire Action and Growth* (first edition). McGraw-Hill
- 3) Dahlander and Gann. (2010). How open is innovation. *Res. Policy*, volume 39, issue 6, pages 699-709.
- 4) Dodgson et al. (2014). *The Oxford Handbook of Innovation Management* Oxford University Press.
- 5) Goodman, J., Korsunova, A., & Halme, M. (2017). Our collaborative future: Activities and roles of stakeholders in sustainability-oriented innovation. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 26(6), 731–753. 10.1002/bse.1941
- 6) Hary Soegiri, Moeljadi, & Yuniarsa, S.O. (2020). The Impact of Innovation and Research and Development on the Transportation Performance: Moderating Role of Supply Chain Management. *Int. J Sup. Chain. Mgt*, Volume 9, No.3, June.
- 7) Klewitz, J., Zeyen, A., & Hansen, E. G. (2012). Intermediaries driving eco-innovation in SMEs: A qualitative investigation. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 15(4), 442–467. 10.1108/14601061211272376.
- 8) Kusterer, David J.; Schmitz, Patrick W. (2017). "The management of innovation: Experimental evidence". *Games and Economic Behavior*. 104: 706–725. Doi:10.1016/j.geb.2017.06.011.
- 9) Moeljadi, Yuniarsa, S.O., Seminar, A.R. (2020). Analysis of A Farmer's Ability on Entrepreneurship to Accumulate Business Capital: Evidence on Jabung, Malang. *Advances in Economics, Business, and Management Research*, volume 144.
- 10) Seebode, D., Jeanrenaud, S., & Bessant, J. (2012). Managing innovation for sustainability. *R&D Management*, 42(3), 195–206. 10.1111/j.1467-9310.2012.00678.x